

ON THE DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF A GRAPHITE/EPOXY VIOLIN

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Over the last decade graphite fibre reinforced composites have found wide-spread applications in the commercial field, particularly in the area of sports and recreation. Potential applications where composites can be successfully utilized are in the making of musical instruments. Graphite in a hybrid construction is already being used in guitars.

In May 1978, as a private venture, it was decided to explore the possibility of designing and constructing a composite violin. This paper describes the effort from initial concept to the construction of two violins in graphite epoxy, and the performance of these instruments.

The program has been successful and rewarding and has shown that there is great potential for the use of fibre resin composites in producing acoustically good stringed instruments that are environmentally stable.

INTRODUCTION

Gasparo da Salo - Gio Paola Maggini - Andreas, Antonius and Hieronymus Amati - Nicolaus Amati - Andreas Guarnerius, Peter Guarnerius, Joseph Guarnerius del Gesu - Antonius Stradivarius - Sanctus Seraphino - Carlo Bergonzi

These are some of the greatest violin makers of the 16th to 18th century from Brescia, Venice and Cremona. It is the unquestioned belief that violins reached perfection at the hands of masters in Cremona.

The violin is as complex as it is variable and each maker has his own peculiar design and a particular signatory 'f' hole. The woods traditionally used are pine and maple, though pear and sycamore also are used. Even with the finest selected wood, variations in properties and tone exist. No two violins are the same, even made from the same piece of wood by the same maker.

The violin has been well researched - the effect and contribution of individual components is well understood and the acoustics, too, have been exhaustively studied. With current technology and a better understanding of material properties and the effect of finishes, present day makers produce fine instruments. However, although the violin can be studied and understood, it has not been possible to design a violin to yield a predictable performance. Even with present day technology, the complexity of integrating the known acoustics into the design concept necessitates, in the end, a 'build and try' approach.

Age is a major variable in the properties and acoustics of the violin and some of the greatest violins, typically those 300 years of age, will deteriorate in performance at some point in the future. Few of the priceless originals are used for their intended purpose; instead, for reasons of preservation, they are kept in temperature and humidity controlled vaults. Since the 18th century the rise in musical pitch has been appreciable and the strength of the old instruments has been insufficient to withstand the effect of the increased tension in the strings. This has resulted in lengthening and thickening of the bass bar.

Having thoroughly studied conventional violin making and the history of the violin, it became apparent that to try to improve on the design of the old masters would be futile. Instead, it was decided to take a fresh look at the violin from the materials standpoint, particularly for a material which would be insensitive to the type of environment to which a violin is exposed. Further, consistent material properties would ensure repeatable acoustics. Otherwise, the violin would be built in a traditional manner, following the design of an old master.

In the summer of 1978, together with Robert F. Innes*, a violin maker of repute, it was decided to explore the possibility of using high modulus fibres in an epoxy matrix for the main acoustic box. The remainder of the violin would be made of traditional materials.

DESIGN APPROACH

We decided that the acoustic box, the belly (top), back (bottom) and the side members, would be made using composite material. The remainder of the violin would be made from traditional materials - the neck and hand carved scroll from curly maple, the fingerboard, tailpiece and tailpin from ebony, and the bridge also from maple.

The top of the traditional violin is removable to enable resetting of the neck and repairing of cracks, etc., when required. In the case of this composite violin, we planned to use structural epoxy adhesive for all joints and to permanently bond the top.

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In constructing a composite violin there are a number of variables that will affect the performance - the choice of fibre reinforcement, the form (unidirectional or fabric), the matrix, the fibre volume, the variation in properties related to fibre orientation, the number of plies, the method of bagging and the cure pressure. With so large a number of interrelated variables, the task seemed difficult and here we relied on intuition and experience.

As a starting point, we made a choice of material, thickness, orientation and cure cycle and, based on the performance of the instrument, we would have many avenues for optimization. Two violins were planned, both the same model but of differing thicknesses, which would give us some comparison of performance related to thickness.

MATERIALS AND TOOLING

After careful consideration, we selected graphite as the reinforcing fibre, as we felt that Kevlar^{*} would have a damping effect while glass lacked the stiffness.

The material used for the violin was unidirectional, epoxy preimpregnated, high modulus graphite (T-300) from Fiberite Corporation. The resin system was 121°C (250°F) curing. All joints on the violin were made using a structural epoxy adhesive.

The violin is based on a Joseph Guarnerius del Gesu. There is an original Guarnerius violin in the Innes family and, using the dimensions from this instrument, a male master representing the belly and the back was hand carved by R. F. Innes. From this we took a female splash and produced a high temperature, glass/epoxy tool. The tool was carefully hand finished so as to impart a good surface on the graphite. The side members consist of the upper, centre and lower bouts. For these side members we used a male mould.

DEVELOPMENT, FABRICATION AND CONSTRUCTION

A small scale development program was carried out to assess the number of plies, the fibre orientation, the bagging procedures and finishing operations, including bonding and cutting out the f-holes. The constructions finally selected were a 6 and an 8 ply (crossplied). Also planned carefully at the development stage was each subsequent step leading up to the careful jiggging required during the assembly bonding operations.

A wood violin graduates in thickness (typically) from 2.38 mm (3/32 in.) at the edge to 3.18 mm (1/8 in.) at the centre for the belly and from 1.59 mm (1/16 in.) at the edge to 4.76 mm (3/16 in.) at the centre for the back. The belly, back and sides of the graphite violins are of constant thickness. This is a departure from tradition but the wood thickness graduation has evolved from a basic strength requirement because of string tension and the downward force transmitted from the strings via the bridge. It is also noted that this thickness graduation affects the stiffness and, hence, vibration characteristics.

Conventional lay-up and bagging techniques were employed and the part was cured at 121°C (250°F) using low pressure.

With the belly, back and side members laid up and cured in the two thicknesses, we proceeded with cutting out the f-holes. These were carefully marked on the graphite and were cut out and finished using tungsten carbide tipped drills and Swiss files. With unidirectional graphite splintering so readily, this was a painstaking operation.

The bass bar in a wood violin is used to transmit the vibrations communicated to it by the left foot of the bridge to the entire belly and so prevent segmental

^{*} DuPont T.M.

vibrations. The bass bar is made of soft, even grained pine and is about 267 mm (10½ in.) long and 4.76 mm (3/16 in.) wide. Its height is 9.53 mm (3/8 in.) in the centre or deepest part. This bar extends along the underside of the belly in a slightly oblique direction and passes underneath the left foot of the bridge. On these two graphite violins we left the bass bar out as we felt that the stiffness of the graphite, together with the fibre orientation, would ensure good communication; however, further evaluation would confirm this one way or the other.

The side members were first bonded to the back and then the fingerboard (including the neck and scroll), finally followed by the belly. The most difficult operation was in the accurate jiggling required for bonding. All bonding was carried out with a room temperature curing, slightly flexibilized, structural epoxy adhesive.

The surface finish on the cured graphite was very good and there was no intention of applying any kind of finish. In fact, it is the varnish on many violins which changes the tone as the damping effect is altered with aging.

On completing the violins, the sound posts were positioned under the E strings (right foot of the bridge). The sound post has been said to constitute the nervous system of the violin, as the tone of the violin depends very much upon the length and position of this part. These posts were made from 6.35 mm (1/4 in.) diameter, even grained pine. Incorrect positioning of the sound post can result in "wolf notes" being produced.

The weights of both of these instruments have turned out to be close to those of conventional violins.

With the tailpin and ebony tailpiece in place, and the bridge in position, the violins were strung with the finest 'Pirastro' strings (G,D,A,E) and tuned. The two violins were completed and ready to play in May 1979.

The natural colour of graphite, together with the black ebony fingerboard and tailpiece, results in a uniquely pleasing appearance. There is usually a surprised reaction when violinists first see the instruments and the question has been raised by some as to whether we can change the colour. We do not plan to apply any finish to these violins. A conventional violin is undoubtedly a beautiful instrument and this is certainly reflected by the finish on the wood. On these graphite violins the acoustic boxes are black but otherwise the instruments are finished conventionally.

PERFORMANCE

In order to study the performance in detail we need to carry out an acoustic analysis by investigating the sound waves and studying the vibration characteristics. Comparisons could be made to data obtained from a master violin which would be used as a reference. With this data base, the composite violins could be modified and the effects of these modifications then studied. In spite of the above, the final proof will be in the assessment by the performer and this too will vary from person to person.

Over the last two centuries a louder tone has evolved in order to fill the present day size of concert halls. The musical tone is a mixture of tones, the lowest of which is the fundamental or first partial tone which gives the pitch, and a series of harmonics or upper partial tones. If the fundamental tone is weak and the partials are strong, shrillness results. A shrill violin will carry well. High partial tones are often preferred for orchestral playing.

Saunders (1), in his classic work in the thirties, carried out detailed acoustic analyses on many violins. He examined many of the best masters' violins, along with some good and bad modern examples, in an attempt to find differences in behaviour.

To date the graphite violins have been played by one internationally renowned violinist and by three artists of concert calibre. They have been played in relatively small rooms and also in Toronto's Massey Hall. Both the instruments perform very well - the overall 'balance' of sound is good, with excellent high notes. The violin of 8 ply construction has more carrying power and is more suited to a large concert hall - other than that, it is difficult to distinguish differences by ear.

It has been commented that the G note needs more depth and that the bass bar should not have been eliminated. Note that, when played, these two instruments are being compared to some of the finest masters, in particular a Stradivarius, a Guarnerius and a Gagliano.

It is further important to note that no adjustments have been made to the sound post or the bridge. The tone of a violin is dramatically affected by the position of the sound post and the shape, height and weight of the bridge. The height of the bridge determines the passage of the vibrations from the strings into the body and, hence, the resultant sound.

It is intended to experiment with adjustments to the bridge and soundpost in an effort to further improve the performance of the violins but there are no plans as yet to alter the material, fibre orientation or manufacturing technique.

Figures 1 and 2 show the two violins. The only unfinished area is the cosmetic edge dressing (the purfling on a conventional violin). Here we plan to have a simple blunt edge.

CONCLUSIONS

Results to date are very promising and we are continuing to further improve the performance. These are hand made violins, built with the care and craftsmanship required for conventional violins. The major difference lies in the fact that the acoustic box is not hand carved but is a composite lay-up instead. On a wood violin, to carve the belly and the back takes an average of 40 hours each and approximately 20 hours for the side pieces, a total of about 100 hours. The acoustic box in graphite can be produced in about 25 hours and this would include cutting out the f-holes. The material cost would be less for a graphite violin when compared to the cost of selected woods used for violins, particularly curly maple.

A violin is a delicate musical instrument that is handled with care and we foresee no impact damage problems related to graphite. In fact, the instrument is stronger and more impact resistant than a violin made of wood. This, together with its insensitivity to the environment (humidity, temperature and aging) makes it an attractive alternative to conventional violins.

We believe these two graphite epoxy violins to be the only ones in existence and are not aware of any other work along similar lines. The exercise has been very rewarding and we foresee great potential in the use of fibre/resin composites to produce acoustically good stringed instruments that are environmentally stable and which will maintain consistency with age.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

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